

Synthesis and spectral studies of mixed ligand complexes $\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_2\text{L}$

R. N. Prasad* and Kirti Mohan Sharma

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : rnp_1949@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received 18 June 2007, accepted 28 September 2007

Abstract : Mixed ligand complexes of the type $[\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_2\text{L}]$ (where acacH = acetylacetonate and HL = salicylaldehyde, 5-bromo-(5-chloro- or 5-nitro-)salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyacetophenone, 2-hydroxypropiophenone, benzoylacetone or dibenzoylmethane) have been synthesized by the reactions of $\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_3$ with the corresponding carbonyl compounds in 1 : 1 molar ratios. These complexes have been characterized by IR, electronic spectroscopy and fast atom bombardment mass spectrometry. They exhibit less intense molecular ion $[\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_2\text{L}^+]$ peaks, however, very strong peak due to the fragment $\text{Cr}(\text{acac})^+$ is observed. Peaks due to other fragments e.g. $\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_2^+$, CrL_2^+ , $\text{Cr}(\text{acac})\text{L}^+$ are also observed. Oligomeric species such as $\text{Cr}_2(\text{acac})_3^+$, $\text{Cr}_2(\text{acac})_4^+$ are also formed.

Keywords : Chromium, mixed ligand complexes, FAB mass spectra, IR spectra, electronic spectra.

Introduction

Mixed ligand complexes of Cr^{III} with acetylacetonate or substituted acetyl acetone and N-containing ligands have been synthesized¹⁻⁴. Mass spectral studies of acetylacetonates and substituted acetylacetonates of Cr^{III} and other metals have been carried out⁵⁻⁹. However, the mass spectra of mixed ligand complexes of Cr^{III} with β -diketones and other ligands have not been reported so far. We have carried out the reactions of $\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_3$ with various carbonyl compounds, which result in the formation of mixed ligand complexes $[\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_2\text{L}]$ (1a-f and 2a-b). Fast atom bombardment mass spectra of these com-

(2)

(a) R = CH_3

(b) R = C_6H_5

plexes have been recorded and the results are described in the present paper.

Results and discussion

The reactions of $\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_3$ with salicylaldehyde, 5-bromo-(chloro- or nitro-)salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyacetophenone, 2-hydroxypropiophenone, benzoylacetone or dibenzoylmethane in 1 : 1 molar ratios result in the formation of mixed ligand complexes of the type $[\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_2\text{L}]$. These complexes are brown solids and are insoluble in chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, benzene, nitrobenzene and methanol but soluble in DMF. The analyses and characteristics of the complexes are recorded in Table 1. The conductances of the complexes are very low ($2-6 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) indicating their non-electrolytic nature¹⁰. The μ_{eff} values of the complexes at 302 K are in the range (4.00-4.46 B.M.) suggesting octahedral geometry around Cr^{III} .

(1)

R	X
(a) H	H
(b) H	Br
(c) H	Cl
(d) H	NO_2
(e) CH_3	H
(f) C_2H_5	H

Table 1. Analyses and characteristics of mixed ligand complexes of Cr^{III}

Sl. no.	Complexes Molecular formula Mol. Wt.	Colour and decomp. temp.	Yield (%)	Metal (%) :			Molar conductances ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
				Found (Calcd.)				
				Metal	C	H		
1.	[Cr(acac) ₂ (sal)] C ₁₇ H ₁₉ O ₆ Cr 371.33	Brown (178)	47	14.03 (14.00)	54.92 (54.98)	5.11 (5.15)	3	4.18
2.	[Cr(acac) ₂ (hap)] C ₁₈ H ₂₁ O ₆ Cr 385.35	Brown (198)	64	13.31 (13.49)	56.04 (56.10)	5.39 (5.49)	3	4.46
3.	[Cr(acac) ₂ (hpp)] C ₁₉ H ₂₃ O ₆ Cr 399.38	Brown (188)	51	13.17 (13.01)	57.06 (57.14)	5.72 (5.80)	5	4.01
4.	[Cr(acac) ₂ (5-Brsal)] C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₆ BrCr 450.22	Brown (196)	32	11.56 (11.54)	45.29 (45.35)	3.96 (4.02)	2	4.46
5.	[Cr(acac) ₂ (5-Clisal)] C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₆ ClCr 405.86	Brown (182)	32	12.68 (12.81)	50.25 (50.35)	4.42 (4.47)	6	4.04
6.	[Cr(acac) ₂ (5-NO ₂ sal)] C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₈ NCr 416.38	Brown (244)	30	12.56 (12.48)	48.94 (49.03)	4.28 (4.35)	3	4.07
7.	[Cr(acac) ₂ (bzac)] C ₂₀ H ₂₃ O ₆ Cr 411.39	Brown (190)	37	12.56 (12.63)	58.31 (58.39)	5.55 (5.63)	3	4.00
8.	[Cr(acac) ₂ (dbzm)] C ₂₅ H ₂₅ O ₆ Cr 473.46	Brown (184)	40	10.86 (10.98)	63.33 (63.42)	5.25 (5.32)	2	4.44

Infrared spectra : The IR spectra of Cr^{III} mixed ligand complexes exhibit strong absorption bands in the region 1580–1650 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to coordinated $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$. In free acetylacetonate and benzoylacetonate the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ band¹¹ has been reported at 1724 cm⁻¹ and in 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ band appears at 1680 cm⁻¹. $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ absorption bands for free salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyacetophenone, 2-hydroxypropiophenone, acetylacetonate and benzoylacetonate occur at 1680, 1660, 1650, 1724 and 1724 cm⁻¹ respectively¹². Thus the shifting of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ to lower wave number side in the mixed ligand complexes supports the chelation of these ligands to the metal atom. Shifting of these bands to lower wave number side on complexation has been reported in case of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} acetylacetonates^{13,14}. Bands in the region 1470–1580 cm⁻¹ in the mixed ligand complexes of Cr^{III} may be assigned to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$. Strong to medium intensity absorption bands in the region 400–600 cm⁻¹ which are not present in the free ligands¹⁵ may be attributed to

$\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ vibrations. Various ¹⁸O labeled acetylacetonates of Cr^{III} show bands at 1520 cm⁻¹ due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$, a 1570 due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ and between 415–660 cm⁻¹ due to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ vibrations¹⁶.

Electronic spectra : Electronic spectra of Cr^{III} complexes were recorded in DMF. Four bands are observed at 250–300, 350–400, 550–600 and 650–700 nm which can be assigned to ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g} (P)$, ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g} (F)$ and ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g} (F)$ transitions and charge transfer respectively. Bands at 550–600 nm are assigned to ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g} (F)$ transitions in substituted tris(acetylacetonates) of chromium¹⁷. Bands occur at 350–450 and 550–600 due to ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g} (F)$ and ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g} (F)$ transitions respectively in β -diketonates of Cr^{III}¹⁸. Various ligand field parameters have been calculated for Cr^{III} complexes. The value of first spin allowed transition (ν_1) at $\sim 17000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is directly taken as $10 Dq$. The value of Racah parameter (B), can be calculated by the equation of Underhill and Billing¹⁹.

Table 2. Electronic spectral data of mixed ligand complexes of Cr^{III}

Complexes	Transition (cm ⁻¹)			10 Dq (cm ⁻¹)	B (cm ⁻¹)	β ₃₅
	⁴ A _{2g} (F) → ⁴ T _{2g} (F) (ν ₁)	⁴ A _{2g} (F) → ⁴ T _{1g} (F) (ν ₂)	⁴ A _{2g} (F) → ⁴ T _{1g} (P) (ν ₃)			
[Cr(acac) ₂ (sal)]	17064	25316	35076	17064	613	0.67
[Cr(acac) ₂ (hap)]	17774	25668	35416	17774	517	0.56
[Cr(acac) ₂ (hpp)]	17857	25773	35817	17857	534	0.58
[Cr(acac) ₂ (5-Brsal)]	17825	25706	35783	17825	534	0.58
[Cr(acac) ₂ (5-Clal)]	17510	25680	35268	17510	561	0.61
[Cr(acac) ₂ (5-NO ₂ sal)]	17772	25672	35424	17772	518	0.56
[Cr(acac) ₂ (bzac)]	17652	25442	35389	17652	525	0.57
[Cr(acac) ₂ (dbzm)]	17558	25414	35364	17558	540	0.59

$$B = (\nu_3 + \nu_2 - 30 Dq)/15$$

The values of Racah inter-electronic repulsion parameters (*B*) are ~ 550 ± 100 (Table 2). These values were compared against the value (918 cm⁻¹) for the free Cr^{III} ion, which indicate considerable covalent character of the metal-ligand bonds in these complexes with the covalency factor (β₃₅ for spin allowed transitions) varying in the range (0.6 ± 0.1).

FAB mass spectra : FAB mass spectra of three complexes [Cr(acac)₂(hap)] (1), [Cr(acac)₂(hpp)] (2) and [Cr(acac)₂(bzac)] (3) have been recorded. The *m/z* values of the peaks along with their intensities relative to the base peak are given in Table 3. Mass spectrum of [Cr(acac)₂(bzac)] is reproduced in Fig. 1. Peaks at *m/z* 136, 137, 154, 289 and 307 are due to NBA matrix. All the complexes exhibit molecular ion (M⁺) peaks of low intensity (1, *m/z* 385, 1.4%; 2, *m/z* 399, 2.8% and 3, *m/z* 411, 3.7%). Sasaki and coworkers⁵ have studied the mass spectra of various metal acetylacetonates and have observed that for the central metal atoms having electro-

negativities between 1.6–1.8, molecular ion peak was of very low intensity or was not observed. In all the three complexes of Cr^{III}, the base peak is observed at *m/z* 250 due to the species Cr(acac)₂⁺ which is formed by the loss of the other ligand moiety from the molecular ion (M⁺). Cr(acac)₃ has been reported to give base peak at *m/z* 250 due to [Cr(acac)₂⁺]^{2,3}. Similarly, the base peak due to Cr(acacX)₂⁺ has been reported in the mass spectra of Cr(acacX)₃⁶⁻⁸ (where X = Cl, Br, I). Loss of CH₃ from this species gives a peak at *m/z* 235 due to [Cr(acac)₂-CH₃]⁺⁹. Loss of acetylacetonate moiety from Cr(acac)₂⁺ gives Cr(acac)⁺ which exhibits quite strong peak at *m/z* 151 (1, 19.4%; 2, 50%; 3, 86.1%). Removal of acetylacetonate moiety from the molecular ion (M⁺) results in the formation of Cr(acac)L⁺ which gives less intense peak in complexes 1 (*m/z* 286, 8.3%) and 2 (*m/z* 300, 6.9%) while an intense peak is observed in the complex 3 (*m/z* 312, 22.2%). Further loss of another acetylacetonate moiety gives the species CrL⁺ which again exhibits less intense peak in all the three complexes (1, *m/z* 188, 1.4%; 2, *m/z* 201, 2.8% and 3, *m/z* 213, 2.8%).

Table 3. Mass spectral data of mixed ligand complexes of Cr^{III} (*m/z* values and relative abundances)

Ion	Cr(acac) ₂ (hap)	Cr(acac) ₂ (hpp)	Cr(acac) ₂ (bzac)
M ⁺ [Cr(acac) ₂ L ⁺]	385 (1.4%)	399 (2.8%)	411 (3.7%)
Cr(acac) ⁺	151 (19.4%)	151 (50%)	151 (86.1%)
CrL ⁺	188 (1.4%)	201 (2.8%)	213 (2.8%)
Cr(acac) ₂ ⁺	250 (100%)	250 (100%)	250 (100%)
CrL ₂ ⁺	322 (1%)	350 (52.8%)	374 (2.7%)
Cr(acac)L ⁺	286 (8.3%)	300 (6.9%)	312 (22.2%)
[Cr(acac) ₂ -CH ₃] ⁺	235 (2.8%)	235 (5.5%)	235 (11.1%)
Cr ₂ (acac) ₃ ⁺	401 (4.6%)	401 (4.6%)	401 (6.0%)
Cr ₂ (acac) ₄ ⁺	500 (2.8%)	500 (5.5%)	500 (5.0%)

L = hap, hpp or bzac.

Fig. 1. Mass spectrum of $[\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_2(\text{bzac})]$.

However, in complex **3** very strong peaks at m/z 349 (59.7%) and m/z 350 (61.6%) are observed due to $[\text{Cr}(\text{bzac})^+ + \text{matrix} (136 \text{ or } 137)]$. The formation of such species can be explained by the following reactions.

Occurrence of peak due to CrL_2^+ can be explained by the following reaction :

CrL_2^+ shows a less intense peak in complex **1** (m/z 322, 1.0%) and **3** (m/z 374, 2.7%) while in complex **2**, a strong peak is observed at m/z 350 (52.8%). Presence of peaks due to various oligomeric species can be explained with the help of the following reactions :

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyacetophenone and 2-hydroxypropiophenone were purified by distillation. 5-Bromosalicylaldehyde, 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde, 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde, benzoylacetone and dibenzoylmethane were purified by recrystallization from hot ethanol. Ethanol was distilled before use.

Chromium was determined volumetrically by potassium dichromate using diphenylamine as indicator. Specific conductances were measured in DMF at room temperature (30 °C) by a Systronics direct reading conductivity meter-304. IR spectra (KBr) of the complexes were recorded in the region 400–4000 cm^{-1} on a Shimadzu-8400 S spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra were recorded in DMF on a Hitachi U-2000 spectrophotometer in the range 300–1100 nm. Magnetic measurements were carried out at room temperature (30 °C) on a Gouy balance using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{CNS})_4]$ as a calibrant. The FAB mass spectra of the complexes were recorded at CDRI, Lucknow on a JEOL SX 102/DA-6000 mass spectrometer/Data system using Argon/Xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas.

Synthesis of the complexes : To an ethanolic solution of $\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_3$ (4.6 mmol, 1.638 g in 10 ml of ethanol), 2-hydroxypropiophenone (4.6 mmol, 0.704 g in 10 ml of

ethanol) was added with stirring. A clear brown solution was obtained. The pH of the reaction mixture was ~ 3.0 . After stirring for half an hour it was refluxed for 8 h. The solid complex $[\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_2(\text{hpp})]$ which was separated was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure. Similarly, the reactions of $\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_3$ with salicylaldehyde, 5-bromosalicylaldehyde, 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde, 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyacetophenone, benzoylacetone and dibenzoylmethane were carried out to give the mixed ligand complexes of the type $[\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_2\text{L}]$.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the UGC, New Delhi for financial support, the Head, Chemistry Department, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur for laboratory facilities, the Head, Chemistry Department, Banasthali Vidyapith, Banasthali (Rajasthan) for magnetic measurements and the Director, CDRI, Lucknow for C, H analyses and FAB mass spectra.

References

1. D. Banerjee, J. Roy and S. Sarkar, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, **8**, 372.
2. J. P. Collman and M. Yamada, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, **28**, 3017.
3. R. A. Palmer, R. C. Fay and T. S. Piper, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, **3**, 875.
4. N. K. Singh, S. K. Kushawaha, A. Srivastava and A. Sodhi, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. and Nano-Metal Chem.*, 2002, **32**, 1743.
5. S. Sasaki, Y. Itagaki, T. Kurokawa and K. Nakanishi, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1967, **40**, 76.
6. M. Saraswathi and J. M. Miller, *Rapid Commun. Mass Spectrom.*, 1995, **9**, 1101.
7. G. M. Bancroft, C. Reichert, J. B. Westmore and H. D. Gesser, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, **8**, 474.
8. C. Reichert, G. M. Bancroft and J. B. Westmore, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1970, **48**, 1362.
9. J. L. Pierce, K. L. Busch, R. G. Cooks and R. A. Walton, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1982, **21**, 2597.
10. G. N. Mukherjee and P. K. Chakraborty, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2001, **78**, 565.
11. L. J. Bellamy and L. Beecher, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 4487.
12. D. P. Graddon and G. M. Mockler, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1967, **20**, 21.
13. H. Junge and H. Musso, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1968, **24A**, 1219.

Prasad *et al.* : Synthesis and spectral studies of mixed ligand complexes $\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_2\text{L}$

14. R. C. Maurya, D. D. Mishra, S. Mukherjee and P. K. Trivedi, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 1991, **16**, 524.
15. K. Nakamoto, Y. Morimoto and A. E. Martell, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 4533.
16. S. Pinchas, B. L. Silver and I. Laulicht, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1967, **46**, 1506.
17. R. L. Lintvedt and L. K. Kernitsky, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1970, **9**, 491.
18. A. M. Fatta and R. L. Lintvedt, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, **10**, 478.
19. A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", 2nd ed., Elsevier, New York, 1984.